

PYRONES AND RELATED COMPOUNDS. PART IV. SELF-CONDENSATION
OF 1 : 3 : 5-TRIKETONES

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Diacetylacetone and dipropionylacetone undergo self-condensation in presence of piperidine to form dihydroxyacetyl-alkyl-naphthalenes.

It is well known that monoketones $R_1\text{-CO-CH}_3$ (I) condense with itself or with another ketone of the type $R_1\text{-CO-R}_2$ (II) to give unsaturated monoketones $R_1R_2\text{C : CH-CO-R}_1$ (III). Thus acetone gives mesityl oxide (III, $R_1=R_2=\text{CH}_3$). The reaction is brought about by hydrochloric acid gas.

Acetyl acetone, a typical diketone, does not undergo self-condensation in presence of hydrochloric acid but only acetic acid and acetone together with some unchanged acetylacetone are recovered, very likely due to acid hydrolysis of the ketone. To avoid possibility of hydrolysis hydrochloric acid has been replaced by diethylamine or piperidine but acetyl acetone is recovered unchanged. Sodium ethylate also gives negative result. However, Hückel (*British Chem. Abstracts*, 1935, i, 204) condensed acetyl acetone with itself on boiling with very dilute hydrochloric acid to afford 4-acetyl-*m*-5-xylene (V). This is formed possibly through (IV) which in the enolic form loses a molecule of water giving (V) thus :

Diacetylacetone, a typical triketone, has the structure (VI, $R=R'=\text{H}$) (cf. Deshapande, Dingankar and Kokil, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 595; Bedekar, Kaushal and Deshapande, *ibid.*, 1935, 12, 466).

It contains in its molecule two reactive methylene groups. With sodium ethylate it forms its own sodium derivative and with acid condensing agents it forms dimethyl pyrone (VII, R=R'=H). With basic condensing agents like piperidine it undergoes self-condensation like the other mono or diketones to form a product C₁₄H₁₄O₃. This proved to be dihydroxydimethylacetyl naphthalene (X, R=R'=H) obtained by Collie and Myers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 122) through the intermediate benzene derivative (IX, R=R'=H). In the formation of (X) in presence of piperidine two molecules of diacetylacetone one in the enolic and the other in the ketonic form, react to form the intermediate product (VIII) which enolises to (X). Dihydroxydimethylacetyl naphthalene forms a diacetyl derivative which has been found identical with that described by Collie.

The homologue dipropionyl acetone (VI, R=R'=CH₃; Deshapande, Dingankar and Kokil, *loc. cit.*) which with acid condensing agents gives diethyl pyrone (VII, R=R'=CH₃) gives similarly with piperidine a self-condensation product (C₁₄H₂₂O₃) which by analogy is dihydroxydiethylmethylpropionyl naphthalene (X, R=R'=CH₃).

EXPERIMENTAL

Diacetylacetone was prepared by the action of strong baryta on dimethyl pyrone which was obtained from dehydracetic acid by the action of hydrochloric acid.

Self-condensation of Diacetylacetone (VI, R=R'=H) to *Dihydroxydimethylacetyl Naphthalene* (X, R=R'=H).—Diacetylacetone (4 g.) was heated with a few drops of piperidine in a small tube with a loose cork in a water-bath for 1 hour. The water drops formed during the reaction and collected on the cooler parts of the tube were removed from time to time. On cooling, the semi-solid yellow mass was rubbed with benzene and filtered, yield 2.5 g. This was crystallised from boiling benzene or glacial acetic acid as thin yellow needles, m. p. 181°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 5.6. C₁₄H₁₄O₃ requires C, 73.0; H, 6.1 per cent).

The dihydroxy derivative of dihydroxydimethylacetyl naphthalene was obtained by boiling the solid melting at 181° with acetic anhydride and a drop of sulphuric acid. On cooling and pouring the reaction mixture in water, the diacetyl derivative separated as a solid which after crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 169° . This was found identical with that described by Collie melting at 168° .

Self-condensation of Dipropionylacetone (VI, $R = R' = CH_3$).—Dipropionylacetone underwent similar self-condensation like diacetylacetone and gave a viscous oil which on rubbing with dilute hydrochloric acid gave the condensation product as yellow crystalline mass; crystallised from benzene it melted at 122° . (Found: C, 75.0; H, 7.0. $C_{18}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 7.6 per cent).

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Received August 8, 1945.